

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NATIONAL FIELDWORK REPORT

Country: Greece

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1. INTRODUCTION

During the past five years, gender-based violence at work has remained at the margins of public debates about research and higher education and addressed only in the context of specific EU funded projects and initiatives. The Greek Ombudsman, which has been investigating cases of sexual harassment in other employment sectors, noted that in Greece, there are persistent obstacles to addressing GVB at work, including “attempts to cover up incidents by employers, whether or not the accusations are against them or against other employees, fear and hesitation on the part of the victims to make public that they have been victims of sexual harassment, the hesitation of colleagues to support the alleged victims, because of fear of by the employers” (Greek Ombudsman, 2016).

The attitudes towards GBV in Universities and research organisations in Greece have radically changed during the first four months of 2021. In January 2021, the #METOO movement started in Greece, when Sofia Bekatorou -a female athlete- publically denounced her rape by a leading member of the national sailing team that took place several years ago (Greek City Times, 2021). However, the case was dismissed due to statute limitations (i.e. the maximum time after which legal proceedings could be initiated had passed, it started a wave of mostly high profile rape and harassment allegations in the arts and sport, but also in less publicised sectors of employment including Universities. It is not clear yet what the long-term impact of the #METOO movement will be in Greece, but it has definitely transformed how women and men think about the issue and how it is being discussed in public debates and in the media, raising awareness and making more visible different forms of GBV, and measures to protect victims and persecute perpetrators.

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2. MAPPING OF POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

The legislation on gender equality at Universities and research institutions is focused on administrative and procedural aspects aiming to change the gender representation by sex (men-women) in the institutional structures and hierarchies of Universities and research institutions. They respond, thus, to the horizontal and vertical gender segregation and address only indirectly GBV (Anagnostou, 2019, Anagnostou and Avlona 2019). According to Article 1 of **Law 3549/2007**, gender equality between men and women is one of the principles of higher education institutions in Greece.¹ **Law 2839/2000** requires one-third equal gender representation

¹ http://www.et.gr/idsocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1_FG3G1iQCVO9pan7MPpsu8rzSZFxgk-

of at least 1/3 of the minority group (male or female) in all decision-making public bodies, which effectively means that if candidates have the same qualifications, the one from the minority gender group will be selected.² **Laws 3653/2008**³ and **4386/2016**⁴ reaffirm this principle in regard to research institutions and technology committees, the National Committee for Research and Innovation, the Sectoral Research Councils, the Regional Councils of Research and Innovation and the Scientific Committees of Research Institutes. Changes regarding equal representation have been very slow, as the provision of the same qualifications by members of the committees have been used as an excuse to prevent its full implementation.

Significant progress was made in 2019 in legislation. **Law 4604/2019** “Promoting substantive equality between the sexes and combatting gender-based violence” encouraged Universities and research centres to integrate gender in both teaching and research activities. For private and commercial companies, including those in the research sector, the law provides for the creation of the so-called Gender “Equality Badge” to reward initiatives promoting equal opportunities and the adoption of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) (Art. 21). The Gender equality Badge has not yet been implemented. **Law 4589/2019**⁵ Took things a step further by providing under Article 33 the establishment of Gender Equality Committees (GECs) in all Greek Universities. The law stipulates that these are composed of unpaid members of staff and act as consultative bodies to the University senate, schools, and departments. The GECs are responsible for the development of GEPs, the measures to promote gender equality and the fight against sexism, the enhancement of academic communities’ awareness and training regarding gender and gender equality, and the promotion of gender studies teaching and research. The GECs are the main institutions responsible for GBV as they are intended to mediate when allegations of discriminatory treatment or harassment are made and to provide support to victims who report gender discrimination or harassment. However, this law is very recent: in most Universities, the GECs have been recently formed and became more active in response to the Me Too movement, while the only GEP so far completed is the one by the independent research centre ELIAMEP, which received EU funding in the context of the TARGET project, precisely for this purpose (Anagnostou, 2021).

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³ [http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e10NQvxT4pcnZvuL736SAqRm8rzSZFvgk-](http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e10NQvxT4pcnZvuL736SAqRm8rzSZFvgk-d320fRVGmm8kAYi3ORfmaoGOr3yYaaTWDDnkxcPQvNBMtY9T3lvMHxXpABIQE1JCW9FiNmRQQT-Ek_FKIm_8xYoyUzPu6rHny71-Grvf2jRWd266N_BRs6fqsZKaEn1zOuA..)

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⁴ [http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1yFkFQkSI6PHjN4I0I8IMjS8rzSZFvgk-aO-](http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1yFkFQkSI6PHjN4I0I8IMjS8rzSZFvgk-aO-Ic5ae5CykAYi3ORfmarKnS6OdhVv83kxcPQvNBMtY9T3lvMHxXpABIQE1JCW9FiNmRQQT-Ek_FKIm_8xYowC8mWHfWG5eylBklz737XHsIMIHZVCijpNDBBQaJuPUA..)

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⁵ [http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1x4TXjOcdL66ZMC4DwrSFyO8rzSZFvgk-XLICQlaWE9-](http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1x4TXjOcdL66ZMC4DwrSFyO8rzSZFvgk-XLICQlaWE9-kAYi3ORfmarM6Ym_fEOTFnkxcPQvNBMtY9T3lvMHxXpABIQE1JCW9FiNmRQQT-Ek_FKIm_8xYoz44AgpSB4scQ2yHjwQWScGJIVDzlrULSmz0-Vy08OGA..)

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GBV at Universities and research institutions falls within the broader framework of relevant legislation and policies on GBV, especially sexual harassment, in employment. **Law 3896/2010** harmonises the Greek legislation with Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 (Act 3896/2010). It provides a definition of harassment as unwanted conduct related to the sex of a person, which is carried out with purpose or has the impact of violating the dignity of this person and of creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment. The law includes both gender-based harassment and sexual harassment and any "other less favourable treatment" and applies to all workplaces, including Universities and research centres. The Greek Ombudsman is an institution that has an advisory but important role in this respect as it receives complaints, investigates them, mediates between parties, and makes decisions that influence policymaking and court decisions.

Although laws and policies on GBV in employment may apply to relations between members of staff in Universities and research institutions, it is unclear how they might be implemented in relations between staff and students. The Greek Ombudsman dealt recently with a case of a student who was a victim of sexual harassment during an internship by her supervisor. The Labour Inspectorate refused to examine the case as she did not have an employment contract, but the Ombudsman did and found several violations, as the employer did not examine the accused perpetrator and removed the victim as soon as she made an official complaint (Greek Ombudsman, 2020). This case illustrates that there is a gap in the existing legislative and policy framework that needs to be addressed with regards to the responsible body that will receive and examine complaints. Some GECs have taken the initiative to give the Student Ombudsman, which is established by Law 4009/2011, the responsibility to act as an intermediary between students and professors. Students, according to such initiatives, will communicate with him/her by phone or email and discuss issues or report cases of GBV, including sexual harassment. However, it is not clear yet, which bodies will investigate the cases and what the procedures will be, as this seems to be an issue that will be dealt with in the GEPs.

It is also unclear which institutions will be responsible for the national strategy on gender equality and especially GBV in Universities and research institutions in Greece. The General Secretariat Gender of Family Policy, Demographic Policy, and Gender Equality (formerly General Secretariat of Gender Equality) is responsible for gender equality policies in general but is not very active in the field of tertiary education. The Greek Ombudsman's gender equality office is responsible for receiving cases of gender-based harassment at work. The General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GFRT) is responsible for drafting the main policies on research, and in its latest report on this issue, it has included a gender dimension but not specifically in regard to gender-based harassment. As a result of the absence of a centralised institution at the national level to deal with GBV in Universities and research centres, at the moment, the most important actors are the GECs, who will draft the regulations for each University and research institution independently. A Pan-Hellenic committee of GECs, however, has been established to promote coordination amongst them. So far, Greek Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), other than the GFRT, have not addressed issues related to GBV, although they have been following some of the EU principles for equal gender representation in research teams and prioritisation in some areas of gendered themes of research.

Finally, Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) have not addressed GBV systematically and extensively. Data on the subject is scarce and is usually collected when EU funding is obtained specifically for this purpose. Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences has

implemented the EU funded Project *USVReact: Universities Supporting Victims of Sexual Violence*, which focused on focuses mostly on different forms of sexual harassment, including psychological, verbal, and physical. The aim is to raise awareness of GBV in the University and prevent cases of sexual harassment, but also inform potential victims about institutions that provide protection. Its main aim was to raise awareness of GBV amongst staff and students of Panteion and prevent cases of sexual harassment, but also inform potential victims about institutions that provide protection (Zavos, 2018). There have also been some dissertations and small research projects examining specific aspects of GBV, such as cyberspace harassment amongst students for short periods of time (Kalfati Michailaki 2019; Zarafonitou, 2014). However, the systematic collection of data and teaching on GBV have not yet been integrated into existing curricula in Universities and research centres.

3. DEBATES REGARDING #METOO AND THE ISTANBUL CONVENTION

The #METOO movement in Greece has brought to the forefront of public debate some cases of sexual harassment in Universities that have received publicity in the media. Three former students of the University of Thessaloniki revealed in a relevant article and a closed Facebook forum of alumni that they had been sexually assaulted by a now-retired professor of the philosophy department. According to the media, the Rector formally requested the intervention of justice for the investigation of the case and the punishment of the perpetrators (Keep Talking Greece, 2021a and 2021b). There were also reports about allegations of sexual harassment at the Athens School of Fine Arts. In response, the Rector has formally informed the prosecutor of anonymous allegations of sexual harassment in social media and a student committee was organised to collect more cases (Kathimerini 2021).

These cases demonstrated that there are no formal procedures in Universities and research institutions to make allegations of GBV, no awareness-raising mechanisms, regulations and rules for the protection of victims. Especially students, precarious researchers and teaching staff with short term contracts are very vulnerable, and their voices have been excluded from public debate. Student feminist groups have played an important role in giving them a space to participate in public debates, mostly through the usage of social media. It was mainly in informal contexts that allegations of social harassment came to the forefront of public debate and were later also reported in the media. This illustrated that there are no formal mechanisms and procedures to report GBV in Universities.

Several articles appeared on the media, and members of the GECs have been interviewed by the media on GBV after the #METOO started (Athens Voice, 2021, Fotiadi, 2021, Macedonian Press Agency, 2021; Tsaliki, 2021). They exposed the absence of policies and regulations against GBV and the lack of awareness of GBV that exists in Universities and research institutions and stressed the importance of GECs and GEPs. They also organised some online discussions organised on, for example, by the University of Macedonia and the Panteion GEC. During these discussions, several GECs presented their positions and interventions were made mostly by academic and some administrative staff. Although many students attended these events, there were very few interventions by them, and precarious academics were almost absent from them. It is, therefore, still unclear what the long-term impact of the METOO movement will be on Universities and research centres.

The responses to the ratification of the Istanbul Convention in Greece were very positive in general. Although it is referred to in relevant University teaching and articles on GBV in newspapers, it has not influenced the debate on Universities and higher education institutions.

4. PUBLIC OPINION ON GBV

There have not been any debates or surveys on GBV in Universities and research institutions in Greece as the #METOO was more visible in high publicity sectors such as the arts and sports. Data on the subject is non-existent as Universities and research institutions have so far failed to establish monitoring and data collection mechanisms. As a result, the issue remains marginalised in public debate.

There were, however, some surveys on GBV, which have focused on the prevalence of GBV in general amongst the adult population. A survey by DIANEOSIS included students: it showed that 40% of women and 11,3% of men had experienced some form of sexual harassment in their lifetime. Of those who have experienced sexual violence, 26,3% were public servants, and 10,8% were students. For female respondents, 35,4% experienced sexual harassment at work and 35,6% outside work, whereas, for male respondents, it was 18,5% at work and 55,1% outside work. For female respondents, 41% of perpetrators were persons in senior/superior positions, and 21,9% were co-workers, while 39% were unknown persons, 20,3% were friends or acquaintances, and 2,7% were family. For men, only 8,3% of perpetrators were persons in senior/superior positions, and 13,5% were co-workers, while 53,9% were unknown, 28,5% were friends or acquaintances, and 2,7% were family (DIANEOSIS, 2018).

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DISCUSSIONS ABOUT GBV

The pandemic has influenced the discussions on GBV in universities and research organisations as it has made more visible in public debates the issue of GBV. More specifically, the rise in GBV during lockdowns that was reported by international organisations received a lot of media attention and paved the way for the #METOO.

As all Universities and most research institutions remained closed, however, during the pandemic, the issue was raised only in relation to past cases of GBV in Universities, and after the first reporting, they do not seem to have progressed much. The long-term impact of the #METOO in Universities and research institutions will depend mostly on feminist student groups and feminist and gender scholars. They are the ones who will put pressure and keep the discussion going either through the GECs and GEP and/or through less institutionalised activities, debates and awareness-raising events.

5. CONCLUSION

In order to move forward, the Greek government needs to organise a coherent and comprehensive approach to the issue of GBV in higher education and research institutions that will include staff and students. Relevant actors should be involved in policy deliberation, and the organisation of legislative and policy initiatives should be assigned to a specific government body, which will also be responsible for collecting data at the national level from all relevant

institutions. While each university can set its own internal regulations and procedures, a common framework will make sure that victims have access to reporting mechanisms, and their protection will be guaranteed even if they are temporarily working or studying at Universities or research institutions.

At the University level, measures should be taken by the GEC to raise awareness, establish procedures and regulations and improve communication amongst students and staff on these matters. Collecting reliable quantitative and qualitative data on GBV is necessary in order to do so, as it is likely to become part of relevant teaching and research activities. Involving students and student groups in the process will assure a more holistic approach that will include diverse actors involved. If a one-sided approach prevails, which is based mostly on the experiences of permanent staff, the problems of the most vulnerable, i.e. the students and precarious, might become marginalised or even ignored. The legacy of the #METOO can be long-lasting, and its impact can become more sustainable, transforming the dominant gender culture in Greek Universities and research institutions.

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